

THE ROLE OF INVESTMENT IN ENSURING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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Annotation: The term investment comes from the Latin word investire, i.e. to clothe. Within the framework of the centrally planned system of the economy, it was identified with capital investments, i.e. the cost of reproducing fixed assets, their increase and improvement. Investments were interpreted as long-term investments in various sectors of the economy. With the beginning of market transformations, the point of view on the content of the "investment" category has changed, which is reflected in the legislation. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Investments was adopted by the Legislative Chamber on December 9, 2019. Approved by the Senate on December 14, 2019.

Key words: budget, finances, government, budget process, modern, budgeting, solutions.

The role of investments in the economic system is to ensure the following processes: ensuring the structural restructuring of the economy; stimulating the development of entrepreneurship; creating additional jobs; providing financial resources for the development and reproduction of basic production funds; developing individual sectors of the economy and the entire economic system as a whole; ensuring the competitiveness of the country's products; supporting the development of small and medium-sized businesses. The most important role in investment activity is played by investments in fixed assets - capital investments. They are the basis for economic growth. Capital investments are investments in fixed

assets (fixed assets), including the costs of new construction, reconstruction and technical re-equipment of existing enterprises, the purchase of machinery, equipment, tools, inventory, design and survey work and other costs.

The structure of investments in fixed assets and their dynamics is the most important characteristic of investment processes in the country. The volume of production, competitiveness of domestic products, development of the productive forces of the industry, financial and economic results of its activities depend on the size of fixed assets, their qualitative condition and efficiency of use. The accumulated mass of worn-out and outdated fixed assets prevents the possible involvement of spare capacities for the production of competitive domestic products; delays the innovative development of the economy; increases the frequency and scale of emergencies and the damage they cause; reduces labor productivity; leads to a deterioration in product quality; disrupts the balance of the economy as a whole. The renewal of fixed assets requires large-scale investments. Sectoral shifts in investment flows determine the pace and proportions of further economic development.

To solve the problem of attracting investments into the country's economy, it is necessary to purposefully regulate state investment activities and form an effective state investment policy. State regulation of investment activity means forms and methods of an administrative and economic nature defined by law, used by government bodies at all levels to implement investment policy that ensures state objectives of socio-economic development of the country and its regions, increase investment efficiency, and ensure safe conditions for investments in various investment facilities. Investment policy should have a goal, objectives, principles and a mechanism for their implementation. The purpose of the investment policy is the implementation of the strategic plan for the economic and social development of the country. But in any case, the ultimate goal of investment policy is to revitalize investment activities aimed at boosting the country's economy and increasing the efficiency of public production.

The state, through monetary and financial policy, can influence changes in the relationship between investment demand and supply, and, consequently, the amount

of income received from various capital and financial assets. It determines the strategy of investors' behavior in the market of investment goods and, as a result, the structure of the investments themselves. Based on the state of the economy (inflation rate, budget deficit, effective demand of the population for goods and services, etc.), certain concepts of regulating the market of investment goods are applied. The investment policy followed by the state has a huge impact on the development of capital investments in the country, both private and public. It forms the so-called investment climate of the country. The investment climate of a country is the most important indicator determining the attractiveness or, conversely, the unattractiveness of a particular country from the perspective of investors. According to its content, the investment climate is "a complex of factors of a political, legal, economic, organizational, social and other nature that influence decision-making regarding the expediency of investing in the economy of a particular country."

Thus, investments play an important role in the development of the economy of any country, providing structural restructuring of the economy; stimulating the development of entrepreneurship and innovative processes; creating additional jobs; developing and reproducing basic production assets; developing individual sectors of the economy and the entire economic system as a whole; increasing the competitiveness of the country's products. The most important indicator determining the attractiveness of a country for investment is the investment climate of the country. Government measures to create an investment climate and stimulate investment shape the country's investment policy. The investment policy followed by the state has a huge impact on the development of capital investments in the country, both private and public. Let's take a closer look at the state of the investment climate and investment activity in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

References:

- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments" (adopted by the Legislative Chamber on December 9, 2019, approved by the Senate on December 14, 2019)